

Redefining Memory: Energy-Efficient SRAM Designs for AI and Edge Computing

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Abstract

Static Random-Access Memory (SRAM) is a building block in modern digital systems, with high-speed and efficient energy storage solutions for a broad range of applications, ranging from embedded systems to artificial intelligence (AI) applications. In this paper, a comprehensive review and comparative analysis of recent SRAM structure trends across technology nodes, i.e., from 180 nm to 3 nm, are reported. Specific emphasis is laid on the omnipresent 6-transistor (6T) SRAM cell, which is described in the context of its development in the face of read-disturb effects, leakage currents, reduced static noise margins (SNM), and scalability issues pertaining to CMOS technology scaling. We discuss compute-in-memory (CIM) approaches, such as 6TP SRAM and Dual-Wordline architectures, that integrate MAC operations within memory arrays to mitigate the von Neumann bottleneck. Advanced SRAM topologies, such as 8T, 10T, 11T, and hybrid analog-digital architectures, have superior energy efficiency, stability, and fault tolerance. In addition, improvement in sense amplifier design, low-voltage operation, and power-saving strategies such as MTCMOS, transistor stacking, and adaptive decoders are described in the context of their impact on read/write performance and energy-delay trade-offs. In this work, these innovations are categorized as traditional SRAM, low-power optimized cells, compute-in-memory frameworks, and sensing circuit improvement and evaluated in terms of their applicability to AI accelerators, IoT devices, and edge computing.

Keywords: SRAM, Compute-In Memory(CIM), Static Noise Margin(SNM), Sense Amplifiers, Decoders, MAC operations, 6TP SRAM, Read Disturb Issue

1 Introduction

Static Random Access Memory (SRAM) has and continues to play a key role in our current digital world, enabling applications ranging from embedded systems to AI and edge computing as a result of speed and energy efficiency. A 6-transistor (6T) SRAM cell is often selected for its superior performance, area, and power trade-offs in CMOS technologies [1]. As the industry has scaled aggressively and demand for low-power applications such as IoT and mobile edge AI also advances, the current research focus is on improving SRAM robustness & stability and functional capability. To address read-disturb issues, necessary leakage, and issues surrounding scalability, the designs have evolved. As an example, Shah et al. developed a 6TP SRAM-based CIM macro that utilizes PMOS access transistors to achieve high compute density and energy efficiency for BNNs [2]. CIM approaches go beyond a storage location to perform multiply-and-accumulate (MAC) operations. In particular, architecture such as the dual-wordline 6T SRAM allows for execution of multibit signed computation without write disturb, which reduces overall execution time significantly compared to memory accesses, allowing for direct inference of activations with no application-specific storage overhead energy cost for evaluation [3]. Also, ultra-low-voltage (ULV) versions of the 6T SRAM design provide the benefit of operating at or below standard supply voltages [3]. As an example, a previous research paper demonstrated that 6T SRAM devices could operate at a minimum voltage of 0.27 V and still perform its memory function [3]. ULV methods it would provide the opportunity to explore sub-threshold memories, which is a growing research area. Advanced nodes (e.g., 3nm FinFETs) allow the use of folded bitline architectures to develop high-speed pseudo-2-port SRAMs capable of operation up to 4.3 GHz [4]. Advanced cells (e.g., 10T, tri-state buffers) can have significant read stability improvements utilizing low-voltage operation [5]. Mixed-signal and hybrid analog-digital

Figure 1: 6T SRAM

SRAMs are suitable for power-aware embedded systems [6] and non-volatile SRAMs (nvSRAMs) enable instant on/off operations [7]. As an illustrative example, the 11T SRAM can accomplish binary/ternary CAM using low energy with full bidirectional access [8].

configurable sense amplifiers use less delay and dilution by switching between the read and compute mode [9], [10]. The 8T SRAM has high fault tolerance due to low leakage, making it ideal for extreme environments [11]. In order to stave off accuracy losses associated with in-memory computing, maximum-likelihood error correction improves compute SNR in a 6T SRAM cell with low-energy [12]. Further advancement on decoder topologies have decreased power and complexities for high-density memory arrays [13]. Power-saving MTCMOS techniques in addition to stacking and voltage-mode bit lines substantially decreased the write delay and leakage power [14], [15]. Simultaneous device, circuit, and architectural co-optimization can diminish the energy-delay product without significant performance loss [16]. Techniques such as forced sleep or utilizing flip-flop based states in 9T SRAM or high-speed sense amplifiers in a 5nm node can improve array-level energy efficiency [17], [18].

2 COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT CELL ARCHITECTURES

2.1 Conventional 6T SRAM

The 6T SRAM (Six-Transistor Static Random Access Memory) which is shown in Fig. 1 cell is the most common memory cell structure used in high-speed digital circuits, including microprocessors, cache memory, and embedded systems. Its popularity is due to its quick access time, low power consumption, and easy architecture. A 6T SRAM cell holds a single bit of binary information using a latch made by two cross-coupled CMOS inverters. This stored value is preserved while the cell is being supplied with power, which makes SRAM a volatile memory. Due to its compatibility with normal CMOS technology, SRAM has a high likelihood of being the best area consumer on System on Chips (SoCs). [1] 6T SRAM is a form of static random-access memory that is made up of six transistors in a cross-coupled inverter configuration and two access transistors. The transistors provide read and write access to the memory cell. A typical SRAM cell (6T cell) contains six transistors as illustrated in Fig.1. Two inverters in this design are combined to create a latch to hold bits and two NMOS to access bit Bitines. The bit cells are arranged in an array with word lines (WL) on the horizontal direction and bit lines (BL and BL) on the vertical direction [19]

2.2 Functioning of 6T SRAM cell

There are three various operating modes within a 6T SRAM cell. Hold, Read, and Write operations are accessible. [20] In Hold mode, the word line (WL) remains low, which deactivates the access transistors (M5 and M6) and isolates the cell from the bit lines. The stored value is retained by the two cross-coupled inverters (implemented by M1–M4) without any refreshing requirement. The mode dissipates very low standby power and supports data retention provided that there is power availability. In Read mode, the WL is enabled (set high), enabling the access transistors and coupling the cell to the bit lines, which are

precharged to VDD. Based on the stored data, one of the bit lines starts to discharge slightly. A sense amplifier senses this voltage difference and drives out the stored value. The design should not allow this operation to disturb the stored data, ensuring read stability. In Write mode, the WL is high and the bit lines are driven to the target logic levels (e.g., $BL = 0$, $BLB = VDD$ to write '0'). The more powerful bitline drivers dominate the cell's prior state, enabling the new data to be written. Writeability is contingent on the bit lines' capability to flip the internal latch consistently. These three modes combined allow the 6T SRAM cell to store, access, and update data effectively, and hence it is a basic building block for high-speed memory systems

2.3 6TP SRAM Cell

6TP SRAM bitcell is an extension of the standard 6T SRAM cell specifically proposed to cater to issues that have been facing Compute-In-Memory (CIM) architecture—specifically the problem of read disturb, voltage variability in the bitline (VBL), and VBL linearity during high-parallelism access. [2] In contrast to conventional 6T cells employing NMOS access transistors, the 6TP bitcell substitutes them with PMOS access transistors. PMOS devices, having lower hole mobility, enable higher gate overdrive voltages at the same drive strength. This enhances read disturb immunity and allows more rows to be activated simultaneously without inducing unwanted bit flips. In addition to providing linearity and minimizing VBL variability, Metal-Oxide-Metal (MoM) capacitors are located on top of the array and tied to the bitlines during compute accesses. By adding capacitance to the bitlines, current-mode accumulation accuracy is improved without any area overhead. During regular read and write accesses, the capacitors are disconnected in order to maintain conventional SRAM behavior. But because of the more dominant pull-down transistors in the cross-coupled inverters, the 6TP cell can experience poor writability under worst-case process corners. For this reason, a column-level write-assist scheme is introduced by temporarily boosting the ground voltage of the bitcell (approximately 200 mV) during writes. This lowers the gate overdrive on the pull-down devices, making writes robust at all corners. In binary MAC operations, the weights are stored in the bitcell in the form of +1 ($Q = VDD$) or 1 ($Q = 0$ V). [2] For an active input, as indicated by a low-voltage pulse applied to the word line, the related PMOS access transistor charges the bitline or its complement based on the stored value. This establishes a differential voltage (VBL) that effectively performs binary multiplication, which is accumulated in all active cells in the column during the compute phase. In total, the 6TP SRAM bitcell increases the ruggedness, scalability, and energy efficiency of SRAM-based CIM macros, making it a compelling choice for high-density, low-power AI edge applications.

2.4 Single Side Read SRAM

In order to address classical 6T bit-cell low-voltage issues, according to CSEM's patent, we modify the read protocol at a higher level. The read access is carried out from one side (i.e.

only the inverted data stored in the bit-cell is accessed, and not both the data and its inverted value which subsequently are normally used as inputs for the sense amplifiers) [21]. That is, the single-side read 6T SRAM architecture is a variation of the standard 6-transistor SRAM bit-cell but aimed at enhancing robustness and lowering the power consumption in sub-threshold voltage operation. The bit lines bl1 and bl2 are employed during a write operation, but while reading, just the bit-line bl1 is employed. That way, reading static noise margin is enhanced because only one internal loop side is accessed. Observe that with this mode reading just the bl1 no sense amplifiers are utilized but just plain tri-state gates suffice. This also makes the design simpler and more robust while operating at sub-threshold voltage levels. [21]

2.5 8T2C SRAM Architecture

The 8T2C SRAM cell is an independent memory cell optimized especially for low-power CIM, focusing especially on the enhancement of Binary Neural Network (BNN) performance. As opposed to standard SRAM-CIM structures that are generally subject to static current leakage and read disturbance issues, the 8T2C cell introduces a novel charge-sharing mechanism that eliminates such issues with high efficiency. This architecture contains eight transistors and two metal-oxide-metal (MOM) capacitors per cell. It has two modes: a regular memory mode for regular read/write operations, and a CIM mode for performing vector-matrix multiplications directly in the memory. The CIM mode functions in two steps—initially charging internal capacitors from input-weight multiplication outputs, and subsequently performing charge-sharing with bitlines to accumulate outputs. Importantly, the design does not consume energy when the input is 0, which is a big improvement over previous capacitive SRAM-CIM architecture. Synthesized in 28nm CMOS technology, 8T2C SRAM-CIM macro reached 3182 TOPS/W energy efficiency at 0.7 V and 4.7 times more efficient compared to latest state-of-the-art literature. The cell is very accurate at inference with MNIST datasets, supported also by methods such as input regularization and in-memory batch normalization. In addition, decoupling of the compute and storage paths makes the cell highly resistant to variations and read-disturb threats [22].

2.6 Pseudo-2-Port SRAM

To satisfy increasing performance and concurrent data access demands in high-performance computing (HPC), contemporary applications need SRAMs to accommodate simultaneous read and write accesses. 2-port SRAMs, especially pseudo-2-port SRAMs, provide an attractive solution by accommodating 1-read and 1-write access per cycle with a single-port 6T cell structure. This is much less area than actual 8T dual-port SRAMs, which generally consume $1.5\times$ area because of separate read and write paths [15]. This cell architecture is shown in Fig.2. The work of Haraguchi et al. reports a double-pumping pseudo-2-port SRAM using 3nm FinFET technology, which uses the folded bitline multi-bank architecture for speed and memory density operation. The design integrates several improved circuits

such as WL Negating with Shortcut (WLNS), Sense-Amplifier-Enable Inter-locking (SAEI), and Pre-Loading Write Driver (PLWD). All these methods combined are aimed at achieving optimum timing margins and reducing cycle latency to a maximum frequency (fMAX) of

Figure 2: 8T Pseudo-2-Port SRAM Cell

4.3 GHz and memory density of 21.1 Mb/mm² at 1.0 V, resulting in a figure of merit (FoM) of 90.7 GHz×Mb/mm²/V [15]. Furthermore, the architecture enables Real-Time Dynamic Performance Scaling (RTDPS), and as such, it can dynamically scale performance over a broad voltage range. Contrary to typical designs, the pseudo-2-port SRAM efficiently balances high-speed performance and spatial efficiency and hence is a very good application for artificial intelligence and graphics processing embedded memory.

2.7 HST-9T1R SRAM Cell Architecture

Mohammad Mudakir Fazili et al. [7] proposed a novel design of 9T1R non-volatile static random access memory (nvSRAM). The proposed nvSRAM cell significantly improves critical performance metrics such as static noise margin, read-delay, break-even time (BET), and store/restore delay/energy. Schmitt trigger action is enabled during read to mitigate read disturb problem and improve read static noise margin. The cell includes two pull-up transistors (i.e., PUL & PUR), three pull-down transistors (i.e., PDL, PDR1 & PDR2), one feedback transistor (i.e., PGF), and two access transistors (i.e., PGL & PGR). The access transistors, PGL and PGR are controlled by row based word-lines, WLA & WLB respectively. The feedback transistor, PGF is controlled by internal storage node Q with its drain connected to a control signal, FBL. [7]

Figure 3: 10T SRAM Cell Architecture

2.8 10T SRAM Cell Architecture

Sunanda Ambulker, Jitendra Kumar Mishra [5] Proposed the design for a 10T SRAM, which is based on Tristate Buffers. . This paper gives better read stability and decreases read delay compared to the conventional 10T SRAM.

Figure 4: Proposed 11T SRAM Cell

Figure 5: 1KB SRAM Architecture

The proposed design contains six NMOS transistors and four PMOS transistors. The PM1, NM1, PM2, NM2 make up the cross coupled inverters. NM3 and NM4 are the Access transistors. PM3, PM4, NM5, NM6 are combined to make the tri-state buffer circuit. The Fig.3 shows the proposed circuit by Sunanda Ambulker, Jitendra Kumar Mishra [5].

2.9 11T SRAM Cell Architecture

Feng Wei et al. [23] proposed a 11T SRAM, as shown in Fig.4, which mainly consists of three parts: the two cross-coupled inverters (P1-N4), the dual-direction write ports with four transistors (N5-N8), and the decoupled read/compute ports with three transistors (N9-N11). The data stored in the proposed 11T SRAM cell can be read in two directions. For the column-wise read operation, the VRWL of the target column is activated to the high voltage state, and the data is read out by the SAs on the horizontal read bit lines HRBLs, which are charged in advance. Data can be written to the proposed 11T SRAM cell in two directions. For the row-wise write operation, the vertical bit lines VBL and VBLB are set to the opposite voltage states according to the writing data, then the HWWLL and HWWLR of the target row are activated to the high voltage state to write the data to the corresponding SRAM cell. For the column-wise write operation, the horizontal bit lines HBL and HBLB are set to the opposite voltage states according to the writing data, then the VWLL and VWLR of the target column are activated to the high voltage state to write the data to the corresponding SRAM cell. [23]

3 COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT SRAM CIRCUIT ARCHITECTURES

The design proposed by Ikramullah Shah Et Al. shows the 96 x 128 6TP SRAM-based CIM macro. [2]The size of the bitcell is as follows; Length $L=1.8\mu\text{m}$, Width $W = 0.6\mu\text{m}$. The circuit is used to compute Matrix vector multiplication. The Cell architecture used is the 6TP SRAM, which mitigates the read disturb issue. [2] A

Single slope ADC is used to compute partial multiply and accumulate value. The proposed design consists of 96 x 128 6TP Cell array, Metal-On-Metal Capacitors for compute mode, Write drivers, Pre-Discharge Circuits, ADC, Row Decoders, Timing Control Circuits, DRVs and Input Activation Buffers. This circuit is designed in TSMC 65nm LP CMOS process. [2]

Masaru Haraguchi et al. [4] proposed design of a double-pumped 1-read and 1-write pseudo-2-port 6T static random access memory (SRAM) with folded bit-line (BL) multi-bank (MB) architecture, shown in Fig.7, which is demonstrated on 3 nm FinFET technology. The memory density is $21.2\text{Mb}/\text{mm}^2$. In this design first half of the clock cycle is utilized for read operation, and the second half of the clock cycle is used for write operation. [4] An analog-mixed signal multi bit CIM based macro on 4KB dual-wordline 6T SRAM(DW6T) is proposed [3]. This is fabricated in a 55nm process. The design consists of four 1KB CIM blocks, where each CIM block contains four 32×8 compute blocks, which performs

Figure 6: 1KB SRAM Circuit Diagram

accumulation of 16 bit multiplication results. Upon utilization of dual-wordline structure, we can reduce the power consumption and write-disturb issue during computation. The architectural diagram of a 1Mb array using the proposed HST-9T1R nvSRAM cell [7]. The whole circuit is divided into two banks of 512kB each. The local control unit is placed between the two banks, which propagates the sense enable (SAE) and column-decoded signals to the local I/O. [7] The local I/O contains column multiplexer, sense amplifier, and an output latch. Kumkum Verma et al. [24] proposed a 1KB SRAM using a 6T cell at a 180nm technology node, shown in Fig.5. This design used memory bank architecture, where SRAM is divided into four blocks with 256 bits each. The memory bank is selected using ‘Block Selector’ circuit. This circuit is said to reduce the power consumption by 78%, as only one bank will be selected at a time and the rest will be in ‘stand-by’

4 DIFFERENT PERIPHERALS FOR IN SRAM

The design proposed by Rakesh Oayaramji Chandankhede et al. [25], is illustrated in Fig.6, consists of 1KB SRAM contains Address latch, row decoder, row driver, column decoder,

Figure 7: Double pumped pseudo-2-port SRAM circuit diagram

precharge circuit, 32 x 32 cell array, write driver, sense amplifier, read and write control, I/O buffers etc. A detailed picture of some of the peripherals are seen in this design. Let us look into some of the peripherals in detail.

4.1 Sense Amplifiers(SA)

The circuit diagram of Sense Amplifier(SA) is illustrated in Fig.8, the BL and BLB are fed into INP and INN respectively, which further compares the voltages between BL and BLB. The sense amplifier senses the small voltage imbalance and immediately amplifies [8] it back to full digital logic levels (0 or 1), making it possible to read out data reliably. It typically uses positive feedback techniques, such as cross-coupled inverter circuits, to accelerate the amplification process. This contributes to higher memory read speeds and, concurrently, power efficiency.

4.1.1 Symmetric single-ended SA(SS-SA)

Jian Chen et al. [9] have mentioned several sensing topologies, and one of them is the symmetric single-ended sense amplifier(SS-SA). The SS-SA topology requires an additional voltage reference to perform bitline computation [9] This SA structure uses a voltage reference (V_{ref}) for comparing the bitline voltage on computational access. A significant bitline voltage difference (200 mV) is required for efficient sensing, which in turn results in added latency and energy dissipation. It typically enables operations such as AND/NOR

4.1.3 Asymmetric differential SA (AD-SA)

In another topology [9] we use a sense amplifier (SA) that operates in a differential bitline (BL/BLB) mode and uses asymmetric transistor sizes, e.g., skewed NMOS transistors, to sense logic levels. It is called as asymmetric differential sense amplifiers. It eliminates the necessity for a reference voltage and outperforms single-ended sense amplifiers (SS-SA) for computationally accessed data, with a reduced voltage differential (140–200 mV) needed. However, it is still dependent on a correspondingly wide voltage swing, which limits speed and efficiency in normal read access operations.

Figure 9: Latch-type symmetric SA

4.1.4 Cross Coupled CMOS Inverter SA.

Anjali Surkar et al. [10] have explained the Cross Coupled CMOS Inverter Sense Amplifier, as a low-complexity voltage-mode sense amplifier that is widely used in SRAM read circuits. The structure is a cross-coupled pair of CMOS inverters that benefit from high gain during the transient period by positive feedback loops. During the read operation, upon the generation of a large enough voltage difference across the bit lines, the sense enable (SE) signal will enable the amplifier to settle rapidly into one of its stable states. Nevertheless, Surkar et al. [10] observe the following significant weakness: shared nodes between input and output make the circuit highly vulnerable to bitline capacitance. The specific implementation introduces a slow sensing delay since a significant voltage difference must

be established prior to the amplifier being able to latch data consistently. Consequently, the length of time in which the circuit takes to make a decision grows, especially for large bitline capacitance. With the delay that comes with high dynamic dissipation of power, the cross-coupled inverter SA is less desirable in modern memory applications with high speeds and low power.

4.1.5 Latch-type Voltage SA

Anjali Surkar et al. [10] present the Latch-Type Voltage Sense Amplifier, as a novel voltage-mode sensing, which prevents the input-output node cross-coupling inherent in cross-coupled structures. The structure benefits from a differential input stage (transistors M5 and M6) and a cross-coupled inverter latch (M1–M4) to increase output amplification. High-impedance differential input amplifier enables the sense amplifier to be less intrusive to the bitlines and allows faster and more accurate voltage sensing. As mentioned by Surkar et al. [10], when sensing, the small voltage difference on the bit lines is magnified by the cross-coupled latch as soon as the SE signal is activated. The design supports high-speed operation with strong positive feedback and differential sensing, allowing the output to completely switch to VDD or GND. Further, once latching has taken place, the current path is turned off, resulting in a tremendous reduction in dynamic and static power dissipation.

4.1.6 Hybrid mode SA.

Anjali Surkar et al. [10] present the Hybrid Mode Sense Amplifier a new architectural paradigm that integrates current-mode inputs with voltage-mode outputs, hence best leveraging the strengths inherent in both modalities. The input is drawn from the bitline capacitor current in this case, and a cross-coupled inverter is employed to generate a full-swing voltage output. The hybrid paradigm is particularly advantageous to SRAMs that require high-speed operation as well as low power dissipation. The circuit, as per Surkar et al. [10], consists of 11 PMOS transistors and 5 NMOS transistors, with separate transistors for precharging, switching, and amplifying functions. For read operation, bitlines and data lines are precharged at VDD, and circuit switching is by sense enable (SE) signal. The low discharge current is created only when the target cell is a logic '0'. Cross-coupled latch positive feedback quickly amplifies the generated voltage difference. Simulation outputs by Surkar et al. [10] show the hybrid mode SA achieves significant delay reductions—92.8% or more over cross-coupled inverter SAs—and lowers total power dissipation by over 50%. Moreover, the delay is virtually independent of bitline capacitance, and thus such an architecture is very scalable and low-power efficient for current memory designs

4.1.7 Voltage Sense Amplifier(VSA)

Thakurendra Singh et al. [18] classify Voltage Sense Amplifiers (VSAs) into three various architectures: differential type, positive feedback differential type, and latch-type voltage sense amplifiers. VSAs are commonly utilized in 6T SRAM cells for sensing the minimum

differential voltage that appears on precharged bitlines in read operation. Latch-based amplifiers are triggered by sense enable (SAE) signal, following which the small input voltage difference is amplified to full swing. VSAs possess a simple circuit structure and have zero standby power consumption. But they are highly vulnerable to bitline capacitance. From the simulation we observe the sensing delay is increased from 1234 ns to 8223 ns when the bitline capacitance is increased from 1 pF to 10 pF. The proposed VSA design demonstrates a power saving of 23.17% compared to earlier methods [18].

4.1.8 Current Sense Amplifier(CSA)

Current Sense Amplifiers (CSAs) is explained in [18], include a range of types such as current mirror, current latch, advanced current latch, and high-speed low-power latch-based configurations. These configurations are very prevalent in 8T SRAM designs and are current differential-based instead of voltage-based for sensing, thereby enabling improved performance at reduced voltage swings. The CSA configuration operates without the use of standby power and provides better performance compared to Voltage Sense Amplifiers (VSAs) in high capacitance loading cases. The sensing delay of CSAs is increased by a small amount, from 174 ns at a capacitance of 1 pF to 1184 ns at 10 pF. In the work presented, CSAs offer a power saving of 12.77% [18].

4.1.9 Charge Transfer Sense Amplifier (CTSA)

Charge Transfer Sense Amplifiers (CTSAs) work by transferring charge from the bitlines to a storage node and then to the output [18]. CTSAs are advantageous for ultra-low-power SRAM implementations. However, their sensing delay is larger than that of Charge-Sensing Amplifiers (CSAs) and ranges from 265 ns to 654 ns as bitline capacitance ranges from 1 pF to 10 pF. In power efficiency, the CTSA provides a marginal improvement of 2.68% in the proposed 45 nm CMOS realization [18].

4.1.10 Ultra Fast Current Mode Sense Amplifier

The Ultra-Fast Current Mode Sense Amplifier of Thakurendra Singh et al. [18] is designed for low energy consumption in high-speed data sensing. It uses advanced current latch methods and works satisfactorily over a wide supply voltage range (1.8–3.3 V). Its design allows for fast sensing even with very small voltage changes, which makes this ideal for Internet of Things (IoT) and high-speed embedded memory applications. Of all the current sense amplifiers (CSAs) that have been considered, this model is the one with the smallest sensing delay and dynamic power consumption [18].

4.1.11 Clamped bit line SE(CSA)

The architecture features a clamping circuit that limits voltage swings on the bitlines, thereby increasing sensing precision and reducing energy consumption. Such an architecture improves

Figure 10: Dual Mode Wordline Driver Circuit

read stability and speed, especially when there are process and supply voltage fluctuations. The architecture is robust across varying bitline capacitances and is best suited for SRAM implementations that are sensitive to static power [18].

4.2 Dual mode wordline driver circuit

Dual-Mode Wordline (WL), shown in Fig.10, Driver is a key circuit block that supports normal SRAM operation, i.e., read and write operations, and Compute-In-Memory (CIM) mode in the same memory array. Its primary role is to modulate voltage levels delivered to the wordline, depending on the operating mode, with a view to optimize performance and save power. The partial voltage swing is utilized to limit the bitline voltage swing to below 240 mV, which is a condition essential to ensuring linearity during current-mode accumulation and minimizing power dissipation. The dual-mode driver circuitry provides voltage regulation for both operation modes by the selective disabling of transistors. During read/write mode, transistor M3 is disabled while M2 provides a connection for the wordline to full-swing voltages. During CIM mode, M2 is disabled while M3 is used to restrict the high level to VDDL rather than VDD. This efficiency-based design supports effortless switching between computation and memory modes, which increases both circuit performance and overall operation of CIM

4.3 Precharge Circuit

As Paper [6] states, the precharge step lowers power consumption and raises the level of readiness for operation by preinitializing the internal nodes to data access. This enhances

stability as well as energy efficiency, especially under low-power mode. The operation explained in Paper [19] gives a thorough explanation of the precharge process, and as per it, the process is performed with the word line (WL) disabled and the bitlines isolated from the cell. A typical precharge circuit consists of three PMOS transistors that connect the bitlines to VDD. This controlled charging reduces noise, maintains bitline symmetry, and offers equal voltage levels prior to sense amplification during read operations. Document [15] points out that the precharge circuit charges the bitlines (and some- times the word line) with a predetermined voltage, restoring the bitlines to their original state before starting a new write or read cy- cle. Not only does this put the memory cell into a known state but also addresses errors due to voltage differences or residual charges. Once the precharge cycle has been completed, sense amplification typically follows, where small voltage differences between the bit-lines are detected and amplified. Finally, the precharge circuit is needed to facilitate noise-immune and power-efficient yet accurate memory access, thereby lending the basis to reliable SRAM opera- tion in the modern VLSI systems.

Table 1: Evaluation of Different SRAM Cell Structures and Characteristics

	[2]	[5]	[3]	[23]
Cell Architecture	6TP	10T	DW6T	11T
Size of cell array	96×128	-	4Kb	64×64
Area of circuit(mm ²)	0.025	-	0.30975	1424
Power consumption(nW)	373.7	1.3	-	17.94
Operating Voltage(V)	1.2	1	1.2	1.2
SNM(mV)	-	335-390	-	-
Process node(nm)	65	28	55	65

lines are detected and amplified. Finally, the precharge circuit is needed to facilitate noise-immune and power-efficient yet accurate memory access, thereby lending the basis to reliable SRAM opera- tion in the modern VLSI systems.

4.4 Decoders

Decoder circuits are essential in SRAM design for translating ad- dress inputs into specific memory locations. They serve the critical function of selecting one row (word line) and one column (bit line) during read and write operations. In Paper [6], a 3×8 decoder is implemented to handle 3-bit address inputs, enabling one of eight outputs corresponding to eight mem- ory rows. This decoder efficiently directs the read/write operation to the correct memory cell while minimizing power consumption. The design uses CMOS NOR gates, where two NMOS transistors are connected in series in the pull-down network and two PMOS transistors in parallel for the pull-up network. This structure en- hances logical selectivity and energy efficiency in address decod- ing. Paper [26] elaborates on both row and column decoders, us- ing NOR-based logic that operates dynamically—requiring a precharge phase followed by an evaluation phase. When the de- coder enable signal is low, only one

output is activated based on the input address. When the enable is high, the decoder is disabled and all outputs remain low regardless of the input. This configuration ensures precise selection and minimizes unnecessary switching.

5 RESULTS

A thorough survey of SRAM research and development activity shows first the reporting of a 6TP CIM macro built from PMOS access transistors previously shown to achieve 984 TOPS/W and a MNIST accuracy of 96.5% [2]. These performance advantages were attributed to use of improved stability and SNM achieved using 10T/11T cells with tri-state read buffers [5], [23]. Reported improvements through design changes such as pseudo-2-port SRAM using FinFETs [4] and hybrid analog-digital 8×8 arrays [6] further emphasize the value of this research. In more reportable work, Moore’s Law has driven scaling of SRAM circuits, so lets focus on some highlighting techniques. Scaling from 180 nm to 3nm not only reduce area and power consumption, but it severely impairs SNM and stability from 11T or similar designs usable on earlier tech nodes [1], [19]. Identifying techniques to improve power-delay product in such scaling without sacrificing performance many are employing MTCMOS, stacking, FinFETs, and optimally using high-Vt in source src circuit [14], [16], [27]. Contributions of designer-friendly reconfigurable sense amplifiers and 8T2C or similar macros enable 3182 TOPS/W or greater [9], [22]. Most work and test efforts utilize Cadence Virtuoso from the 180 nm to 28 nm nodes and aim change using standard cell applications for SoC, AI, and IoT [1, 4, 6, 24, 28, 29].

Table 2: Evaluation of Different SRAM Cell Structures and Characteristics

	[24]	[30]	[22]
Cell Architecture	6T	6T	8T2C
Size of cell array	1KB	1KB	256*64
Area of circuit(mm ²)	-	-	0.02678642
Power consumption(nW)	1.09–9.05 mW	410 μW	0.225–0.446
Operating Voltage(V)	1.8	0.7	0.7–1.0
SNM(mV)	200	-	-
Process node(nm)	180		28

6 CONCLUSION

This comparative analysis in this research showcases advancements in SRAM design at different technology nodes, with a focus on energy efficiency, stability, and compute-in-memory (CIM) functionality. Ikramullah Shah et al.’s 6TP SRAM-based CIM macro has state-of-the-art energy efficiency of 984 TOPS/W (1-bit MAC) and 157.6 TOPS/W (5-bit

MAC) with PMOS access transistors and MoM capacitors in 65 nm CMOS. Ambulker and Mishra's 10T SRAM in 28 nm improves RSNM and read delay and exhibits better read stability compared to traditional 6T and 10T cells. Likewise, the 8T2C SRAM-CIM macro in 28 nm provides better energy efficiency (3182 TOPS/W) through charge sharing methods. Masaru Haraguchi's pseudo-2-port 6T SRAM in 3 nm FinFET is focused on performance and density, achieving 4.3 GHz and 21.1 Mb/mm². Simulation-based works like those of Mittal and Kalpana et al. indicate that technology scaling from 180 nm to 45 nm lowers power and area but compromises SNM stability. Overall, advancements in SRAM architecture, sensing, and access circuitry at process nodes reflect major trade-offs between performance, stability, energy efficiency, and technology complexity that allow for various optimizations for VLSI and CIM applications.

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